

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Factors that influence the provision of basic immunizations to babies: A literature review

Renanda Dwi Palupi *

Department of Reproductive Health Faculty of Public Health, Airlangga University, Surabaya, Indonesia.

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Abstract

Immunization is a simple, safe and effective way to protect a person from dangerous diseases, before coming into contact with disease-causing agents (WHO, 2019). Providing basic immunizations to babies is very important to prevent diseases that can be prevented by immunization. Many factors influence parents' decisions to provide basic immunizations to babies. This study aims to determine the factors that influence the provision of basic immunizations to babies. The research method used is a literature review, namely searching for research articles from Google Scholar and Research Gate using several keywords, namely basic immunization, influencing factors, maternal factors, infant mortality and diseases that can be prevented by immunization (VPD). From this research, the results showed that immunization for babies was influenced by several dominant factors, namely knowledge (10 articles), attitudes (5 articles), family support (7 articles), support from health workers (4 articles), and access to immunization providers. (2 articles).

Keywords: Basic Immunization; Influencing Factors; Maternal Factors; Infant Mortality; Diseases that Can be Prevented by Immunization (VPD)

1. Introduction

Health is a human right of all humans at all ages. Health is also a major investment in the success of a country's development. One of the priorities in nation development is the program to reduce infant mortality (IMR). Several diseases that cause infant death can be prevented by immunization.

Immunization is a health service that aims to protect individuals from diseases that can be prevented by immunization (VPD) [5]. Getting a complete basic vaccine (immunization) is one of the first steps to prevent certain diseases and is usually given by injection to babies under a certain age [7]. Basic immunization coverage for babies includes BCG, Hepatitis B, DPT, Polio and Measles.

The importance of immunization can be seen from the number of children under five who die from diseases that can be prevented by immunization (VPD) [6]. World Health Data Organization (WHO) shows that every year, at least 1.7 million children die from diseases that can be prevented by available vaccines [9]. The death rate can be reduced if disease is prevented by immunization. Therefore, immunization is very important to do.

Immunization for babies is influenced by many factors. The dominant factor is the factor that influences the decision of the baby's parents because in this case the baby cannot make a choice for himself. Parental decisions are influenced by many factors, both directly and indirectly.

* Corresponding author: Renanda Dwi Palupi

2. Material and methods

This research is qualitative research that uses a literature review method with descriptive analysis. The data used in this research came from national journal scientific articles obtained from Google Scholar and Research Gate with the keywords "basic immunization", "influencing factors", "maternal factors", "infant death" and "diseases that can be prevented by immunization (VPD)". The inclusion criteria in this study were scientific articles published within the last 5 years (2018-2023).

3. Results and discussion

The following are the findings from the articles that have been collected and analyzed.

Table 1 List of Articles

No.	Author	Method	Result
1	Ratna Juwita	Cross Sectional	Factors that have a significant relationship with providing complete basic immunization to babies are: knowledge, attitude, family support, and support from health workers.
2	Ikrimah Pohan, et al.	Cross Sectional	Supporting factors for providing complete basic immunization to babies are: knowledge, trust, traveling time, and the role of health workers.
3	Yeni Riza, et al.	Cross Sectional	Factors that influence the completeness of basic immunization in babies are knowledge and husband's support.
4	Nani Handayani	Cross Sectional	Mother's knowledge, mother's age, and distance from residence to immunization service location affects the completeness of basic immunization in infants.
5	Ratih Septiana Arpen and Nur Hidayah Afnas	Cross Sectional	Factors that are significantly related to providing basic immunizations to babies are: knowledge, attitude, mother's perception, mother's education, family support, and the role of health workers.
6	Kholila	Cross Sectional	Factors that influence the provision of basic immunizations to babies are: knowledge, attitude, and family support.
7	Supar Hendra Hasyifuddin, et al.	Cross Sectional	Influential factors in providing basic immunizations to babies include: mother's information, family support, welfare officer work, posyandu framework work, and local area pioneer work.
8	Angga Irawan, et al.	Cross Sectional	Knowledge, perception, and family support related to the mother's motivation in providing basic immunizations to babies.
9	Muhammad Thabran Talib and Satriani Albar	Cross Sectional	Knowledge and attitude influence the provision of basic immunizations to babies.
10	Maya Febriyanti, et al.	Cross Sectional	Factors that significantly influence the provision of basic immunizations to babies are education and mother's attitude.
11	Puspita Sari, et al.	Cross Sectional	Knowledge, family support, and officer's role influences the provision of basic immunizations to babies.

Based on the results of a review of 8 articles as presented in Table 1, the dominant factors that influence the provision of basic immunizations to babies include knowledge, attitudes, family support, support from health workers, access to immunization providers, and several other factors.

Knowledge is the factor that most influences the provision of immunizations to babies. According to Nani Handayani (2018), incomplete basic immunization occurs more often (74.2%) in respondents or mothers who have poor knowledge about basic immunization compared to mothers or respondents who have good knowledge (10.5%) about

immunization base. This means that the better the mother's knowledge, the greater the possibility of the mother immunizing her baby, and vice versa. Knowledge plays a big role in a person's decision to take action, including action regarding health. This is also in line with research conducted by Ikrimah Pohan, et al. (2023) which proves that the knowledge variable has a sig-p value of $0.007 < 0.05$, which means that knowledge has a significant effect on providing basic immunization to babies.

Another factor that has a big influence on providing basic immunization to babies is family support. Family support is support from all family members, especially the husband. Family support can take the form of moral and material support. Family support also includes facilities to reach immunization provider services. Based on analysis in research by Supar Hendra et al. (2023), obtained a p value of 0.006, which means there is a relationship between family support and completeness of basic immunization for babies. This is also supported by the research results of Kholila (2021) which stated that there were 33 respondents with complete basic immunization out of 44 respondents with high family support and there were 23 respondents with incomplete basic immunization out of 48 respondents with low family support.

Attitude is also an important factor in providing immunizations to babies. Basic immunization for babies is the impact of the mother's attitude towards immunization. This is in accordance with the results of research by Ratih and Nur (2023) which stated that of 50 people with negative attitudes there were 37 (74%) people with incomplete basic immunization and 13 (26%) people with complete basic immunization and of the 41 people with there were positive attitudes in 25 (61%) people with complete basic immunization and 16 (39%) people with incomplete basic immunization.

The role of health workers influences the provision of immunizations to babies. In research conducted by Puspita Sari (2022), there were 77.1% (37 people) of respondents who had incomplete basic immunization status out of 48 responses with the officer's role being poor. Apart from that, there were 64.5% (20 people) of respondents who had complete basic immunization status out of 31 respondents with good health worker roles. In this study, the p value=0.001 ($p < 0.05$) was also obtained, which means that there is a significant relationship between the role of health workers and providing immunizations to babies.

Access to immunization services is also a factor that influences the provision of immunizations to babies. Access to immunization services includes travel distance which affects travel time. A study conducted by Nani Handayani (2018) proved that 74.1% of incomplete basic immunizations occurred in babies with a long distance from home to health services (more than 1 kilometers). Other research also states that the longer the travel time, the lower the mother's chances of immunizing her baby.

Other factors that influence the provision of basic immunizations to children are beliefs, mother's age, mother's perception, mother's education, welfare officer work, posyandu framework work, and local area pioneer work.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of research that has been conducted, there are several factors that often appear and influence the provision of basic immunizations to babies, namely knowledge, attitudes, family support, support from health workers, and access to immunization providers. Based on these several factors, knowledge is the dominant factor in influencing the provision of basic immunizations to babies. Apart from that, there are several other factors, namely trust, mother's age, mother's perception, mother's education, welfare officer work, posyandu framework work, and local area pioneer work which also influence the provision of basic immunization to babies.

Compliance with ethical standards

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